

IPBES VA Ch3. Systematic Review of Previous comparative assessments of valuation methods / IPBES Values Assessment (3.2)

Code: IPBES_VA_3.2

Versioning: 02 (29.12.2020)

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Description: This review corresponds to the IPBES Values assessment. The methodology explained in this report responds to the mandate of Ch. 3 that will assess different valuation methodologies and approaches and will be based on a broad review of valuation methodologies and approaches that have been applied in the different specialised sources of information. Reviews of specific valuation methods and approaches (e.g., contingent valuation, choice experiments) do exist. Yet, those that undertake critical assessments of multiple methods conducted from a wide range of perspectives are scarce if not completely lacking. A critical assessment of valuation methods or approaches from multiple perspectives (worldviews, values and knowledge systems) that could inform biodiversity and ecosystem services related decision-making is missing in previous assessments and existing peer-reviewed literature. Therefore, a systematic review of peer reviewed literature was conducted to identify critical knowledge regarding valuation methods.

Process overview:

miro

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: Systematic Review of Previous comparative assessments of valuation methods

Search terms:

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TS= ((TITLE(Valuation)
AND TITLE-ABS-KEY(review*))
AND ( LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA,"ENVI" )
OR LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA,"ECON" )
OR LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA,"BUSI" )
OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI" )
OR LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA,"AGRI" )
OR LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA,"EART" )
OR LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA,"ENER" )
OR LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA,"DECI" )
OR LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA,"ARTS" )
OR LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA,"PSYC" )
OR LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA,"MULT" ) )
AND ( LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE,"re" ) )
  
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Search languages: English

Search engine: Scopus

Exact search date: June 25, 2020

Sample extracted: 144 papers

Fields extracted:

- Author
- Title
- Year
- Journal
- Abstract
- Cited by
- DOI
- Link

Location and format of the data: [IPBES VA 3.2 25.06.20 \(A\)](#)

Treatment applied: (R1) A close examination of the abstracts, introductions and conclusions of these papers was used to identify the relevant papers for the purpose of this section. This process resulted in 51 papers. However, 10 papers were excluded due to their unavailability or language, resulting in a total of 41 papers for further analysis.

Sample extracted (A): 41 papers

Location and format of the data: [IPBES VA 3.2 25.06.20 \(B\)](#)

Analysis of the data: Qualitative analysis of these papers was performed and summarised in 3.1.3. Previous assessments and significant reviews of valuation methods.

Documents attached:

ID	Name	File type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_3.2_25.06.20_(A)	.xls	109 kb	Database with the 144 papers retrieved from SCOPUS
B	IPBES_VA_3.2_25.06.20_(B)	.xls	34 kb	Database with the 41 papers selected
